

LOD-GEOSS Deliverable D5

Software and Data Integration

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1 Introduction

1.1 Context

The overarching intent behind the LOD-GEOSS project's pursuit of linked open data in the field of energy systems research, is to enable efficient and high-quality research. Only through the publication and good description of research data can applied methods and achieved results be found, traced, reused and further improved. The open exchange of research data provides opportunities to address the extensive and heterogeneous data needs in energy systems analysis while avoiding unnecessary duplication of efforts. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship help to break down this abstract goal into individual requirements that can be addressed more concretely (Wilkinson et al. 2016). The requirements of findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability are not only directed at the contents and structures of the research data themselves, but also at the research data infrastructure in particular. With the development and establishment of the DBpedia Databus¹ as a connecting link in a distributed data infrastructure, the LOD-GEOSS project makes a significant contribution to improving the findability and accessibility of datasets within the domain of energy systems research.

1.2 Challenges

However, even when data is found, it often requires considerable effort to feed it into modeling software. Contents and structures of datasets are usually only captured by metadata in an abstract way, so that the data must first be downloaded, opened and inspected in order to assess their suitability for a model calculation. The same applies to the subsequent use of software models. Here, too, it is often only clear to the respective developers, which data contents and models are required by individual interfaces in order to guarantee error-free processing. However, information of this kind is essential for the integration of data and research software. Only if it is known in which format data are available and in which they are required, can transformation needs be determined and suitable transformation functions identified. The integration of software and data is a challenge, especially in energy systems research. Large differences in perspectives and levels of detail, individual data models and interfaces, and inconsistently applied description structures and terminologies hinder the subsequent use and combination of research data artifacts.

¹<https://databus.dbpedia.org/>

1.3 Goals

It was part of the ambition of the LOD-GEOSS project – and the main objective of deliverable D5 – to simplify not only the actual retrieval of datasets but also their conveyance into the models of energy systems research. For this purpose, an open and flexible integration concept should be developed and implemented exemplarily, which closes the gaps between heterogeneous database and model interfaces and consolidates data transformation efforts that have not been sustainable so far. In order to support the application of this concept in the everyday execution of even complex model experiments, it was further the aim to develop practical design and action recommendations and to supplement these with an overview of relevant already existing or specially developed tools.

1.4 Software and data integration concept

For the successful introduction and use of a distributed energy data infrastructure, the DBpedia Databus must be supplemented by additional building blocks in its function as a data registration platform (cf. figure 1.1).

Ontologies and controlled vocabularies are needed as a collaboratively defined linguistic basis on which to unambiguously annotate research data artifacts. For energy systems analysis, particular reference should be made to the Open Energy Ontology (OEO) which has been introduced in an article by [Booshehri et al. \(2021\)](#) and the development of which was also strongly supported by this project. Furthermore, ontology referencing metadata schemas are needed, which can be used to list all information considered relevant by the domain to describe artifacts in a well-structured and machine-actionable format. In order to enable an overarching integration, research models, especially their software interfaces, must be described in addition to individual files on repositories and individual datasets within databases. In addition to the unambiguous designation of data content, annotation must place particular emphasis on the data formats, structures, and values comprised or expected. The more uniform the data models are within a research area, the lower the need for transformation when feeding data into models. Finally, the FAIR publication of metadata as technical documentation of research software and data must be supported by tools and at least partially automated processes. If both data and software are discoverable and well described, flexible scientific workflows for performing model experiments can be created, incorporating transformation methods to ensure interoperability.

The modular approach propagated by the workflow concept developed in this project allows for more detailed description and more flexible reuse of both data and software components. The laborious development of individual non-sustainable interfaces and processing scripts, through which only two specific artifacts can be linked, is replaced by the reuse of transformation functions that can be dynamically deployed and jointly evolved.

This document is structured as follows: Chapter 2 deals with the description

Figure 1.1: A workflow-based concept for software and data integration in interaction with the individual components of a distributed data infrastructure.

of research software by first going into metadata explicitly designed for software and then discussing how it can be generated and published. Chapter 3 is structured accordingly, which deals with the metadata description of datasets. Chapter 4 uses relational databases and RDF triple stores as examples to show how individual database contents can be annotated and registered on a comprehensive catalog platform. Chapter 5 describes workflow-based integration of software and data, in which interoperability is established through modular transformation functions. Chapter 6 concludes by listing recommendations for action derived from experiences gathered during the course of this project, that promote cooperative scientific information exchange in a domain such as energy research.

2 Description of Software

On the topic of software description, the preprint "A Metadata-Based Ecosystem to Improve the FAIRness of Research Software" was published by [Kuckertz et al. \(2023\)](#) in a cooperation of the LOD-GEOSS project with the projects NFDI4Ing and NFDI4Energy [DFG project no. 442146713; 501865131]. In this chapter, its contents are summarized insofar as they are relevant to the larger project context presented here. For more detailed explanations and examples of the topics addressed in this chapter, it is recommended to consult the original publication. The metadata schema and the open source tools supporting it, which were developed during the cooperation, can be viewed, referenced, obtained, and collaboratively further developed in DataDesc's GitHub repository¹.

2.1 Software metadata

Software metadata is the information that describes a software. They provide information about what purpose a software fulfills, how it was created, where it can be found and how it can be used. They can be structured along a metadata schema and are contained within the source code or in stand-alone files attached to a software project. A metadata schema specifies and describes individual aspects by which software can be characterized and thus forms a formal framework that can also be used as a documentation standard. A domain-independent schema for software metadata widely used in research is CodeMeta².

Metadata schemas mostly contain general information, which consists of naming the institutions and people who took part in the creation process, as well as the technical requirements and license conditions. Although they contribute significantly to the findability of software by providing categories and keywords, they do not enable reusability or interoperability of their information in machine-processable form. Internal data models and interface functionalities are not individually represented by them. Standards such as OpenAPI and WSDL, which represent information of this type, focus on web services and protocols rather than research software. The lack of REST-compliant interfaces in research software results in non-standard and non-exploitable interface information being published on web pages that are not associated with regulated vocabularies or ontologies.

With the help of this project, DataDesc was developed, a research software metadata approach enabling detailed semantic machine-processable interface descriptions (cf. figure 2.1). It provides the means to annotate software inter-

¹<https://github.com/FZJ-IEK3-VSA/DataDesc>

²<https://codemeta.github.io/>

face components, enabling insights into data and program usage. The schema promotes reuse and integration of research software, complementing existing metadata schemas. It includes descriptions of functions, data models, and intended and permissible data for interface functions.

2.2 Software metadata creation

Annotating software with metadata is time-consuming, especially if it is done extensively using detailed schemas. In addition, the information is repeatedly collected in the context of its publication or comprehensive evaluations, which greatly increases documentation effort. In order to avoid this and to be able to exchange data once collected in a consolidated and flexible way, an exchange format was developed in LOD-GEOSS as part of the DataDesc ecosystem.

Since it enables a programming language-independent description of software that is human and machine readable, the OpenAPI specification was chosen as its foundation. All metadata about a software can be stored in a single OpenAPI-compliant YAML file (cf. figure 2.2). Its fundamental organization is a hierarchical object tree with two separate sections (cf. figure 2.1). All generic information, e.g. adhering to CodeMeta, can be accommodated in the *info* part. The technical interface metadata, as given by the DataDesc standard, can be specified in the *components* section. In case metadata elements needed for a specific use case are missing, the exchange format allows individual extensions. Furthermore, these extensions enable the annotation of non-REST-conform interfaces and are used to organize and annotate code interface components like classes, functions, and variables in the hierarchy.

There are many tools for documentation that could automatically parse technical interface documentation from source code (e.g., JavaDoc³, PerlDoc⁴, or Doxygen⁵), as each computer language has individual requirements for parsing and interpreting code information. However, available tools rely on code comments that are formulated in natural language and which, therefore, are not directly machine-actionable, or are specifically designed for REST-API structures.

With the help of this project and as part of the DataDesc ecosystem, a Python parser has been developed, specifically designed for the presented exchange schema, enabling the compilation of human and machine actionable metadata also for research software without REST-APIs. It automatically builds the hierarchical object tree from the pertinent code structures and associated metadata, which is then saved in an OpenAPI-compliant file. Together with a browser-based input form to gather general information along the CodeMeta standard, the In LOD-GEOSS developed DataDesc utilities comprise a tool that can merge various DataDesc files, so that the entire description of a software can be represented in a single concise documentation file that is easily exchangeable. The strong interoperability of this approach is based on its OpenAPI confor-

³<https://www.oracle.com/java/technologies/javase/javadoc.html>

⁴<https://perldoc.perl.org/>

⁵<https://www.doxygen.nl/>

Figure 2.1: Structure and content of the DataDesc schema within an OpenAPI-conforming YAML file. While a software is described with *CodeMeta* (blue) in the info section, its objects are described in the component section with *DataDesc* (black), which re-uses terms from *OpenAPI* (brown) and the *Software Description Ontology* (pink). All objects are arranged in a hierarchical structure, which is indicated by arrows pointing from child to parent objects. (Kuckertz et al. (2023), p.10)

```
1 openapi: 3.0.0
2 info: ### Info section
3   title: FINE - A Framework for Integrated Energy System Assessment
4   version: 2.2.2
5   x-first-release: '2018-11-12'
6   x-programming-lang: Python
7 components: ### Components section
8   Component: ### FINE Component class
9     description: The Component class includes...
10    properties: ### Class Variables
11      capacityMax:
12        x-dimensions: &id001 ### Referencable inner Pandas Dataframe structure
13        location:
14          ItemMinimumValue: 0
15          UnitType: spatial identifier
16        time:
17          ItemMinimumValue: 0
18          UnitType: temporal identifier
19 EnergySystemModel: ### FINE Energy System Model class
20   properties: ### Class Variables
21     numberOfTimeSteps:
22       type: integer
23       x-DefaultValue: 8760
24       x-MinimumValue: 0 ### Allowed value range
25       x-ExclusiveMinimum: true
26   required: ### List of required parameters
27   - numberOfTimeSteps
28   x-functions: ### Class functions
29     aggregateTemporally:
30       properties: ### Function parameters
31       clusterMethod:
32         x-ValueSet: ### Allowed value set
33         - averaging
34         - k_means
35       x-VariableRole: input ### Input parameter
36   removeComponent:
37     return: ### Return value
38     $ref: '#/components/schemas/Component' ### Referencing data structure
39   readNetCDFtoEnergySystemModel:
40     properties: ### Function parameters
41     filePath: ### Path to external file
42     type: string
43     x-FileFormat: NetCDF
44     x-NetCDFFolders: ### Inner structure of referenced NetCDF file
45       Input Data: ### Data folders
46       - Conversion
47       - Storage
48     Parameters: ### Control parameters
49     - numberOfTimeSteps
50     - verboseLogLevel
```

Figure 2.2: Compilation of selected lines of code from the YAML file generated to document the FINE interfaces to represent the OpenAPI-compliant syntax and its semantics within the DataDesc schema. (Kuckertz et al. (2023), p.18)

mance, because it may be combined with a wide range of freely accessible tools that also follow this standard.

2.3 Software metadata publication

The publication of software metadata on suitable platforms is crucial for the dissemination, findability, and reusability of research software within and across academic communities. Utilizing multiple metadata publication platforms parallelly enhances software impact and transparency. However, since there is no single widely accepted metadata format, it is sometimes necessary to capture information redundantly and adapt it to different upload processes and file types. The DataDesc approach aims to enable developers to create software metadata and documentation only once and then reuse it at will. To support the publication of metadata on different platforms, individual publishing pipelines have been developed for them. The platforms that could already be prototypically connected to DataDesc within the duration of the project, are listed below:

- SwaggerHub ⁶
- GitHub ⁷
- Python Package Index (PyPi) ⁸
- ReadTheDocs ⁹
- Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG) ¹⁰
- Open Energy Research Graph (OEKG) ¹¹ (pipeline currently in the planning stage)

⁶<https://app.swaggerhub.com/search>

⁷<https://github.com/>

⁸<https://pypi.org/>

⁹<https://readthedocs.org/>

¹⁰<https://orkg.org/>

¹¹<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oekg>

3 Description of Datasets

3.1 Dataset metadata

Metadata is data that describes other data. It contains structured information that identifies, characterizes, and classifies datasets. Metadata records summarize basic information about data that enables its retrieval, interpretation, and reuse. For example, author, title, creation date, modification date, format, and file size are common metadata elements. The ability to filter or search for a specific property makes finding a record much easier. In order to search and compare data across sources, it makes sense to annotate data along metadata schemas. Some common schemas are listed below.

- The DataCite Metadata Schema¹ defines a small set of metadata terms for citing and retrieving datasets and is used by the Registry of Researchdata Repositories (re3data)².
- The Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT 2)³ is defined for increasing the interoperability between data catalogs by consistently describing data catalogues as well as the datasets and data services they include. The spatial and temporal coverage, as well as the spatial and temporal resolution of the data can be described.
- DCAT-AP is an application profile based on DCAT for European data portals. Country-specific adaptations exist (e.g., DCAT-AP.de⁴ for Germany). The Data Quality Vocabulary (DQV)⁵ is an extension to DCAT for describing the quality of a dataset. Currently it is worked on DCAT 3⁶.
- Frictionless Data⁷ defines schemas for the description of data, coherent collections of data, and the structure (schema) of tabular data. The terms of the schema itself are not linked to an ontology or referenceable by a persistent identifier.
- Further terms relevant to the description of data and processing of it can be found in the ontology of bioscientific data analysis and data management (EDAM)⁸.

¹<https://support.datacite.org/docs/datacite-metadata-schema-44>

²<https://www.re3data.org/>

³<http://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat/>

⁴<https://www.dcat-ap.de/def/dcatde/2.0/spec/>

⁵<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dqv/>

⁶<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

⁷<https://specs.frictionlessdata.io/>

⁸<https://edamontology.org/page>

In the domain of energy systems research and as part of LOD-GEOSS efforts, Open Energy Metadata⁹ was developed as a metadata schema that takes into account interoperability aspects in particular. With a focus on tabular data, detailed structural information is collected in the schema. For example, it is possible to describe individual tables and also individual columns in detail. Furthermore, these individual substructures can be contextualized with ontology classes. Definitions and contexts, such as those provided for the energy sector by the OEO, enable a clear interpretation of the data content and minimize inaccuracies and misunderstandings. In this way, the Open Energy Metadata schema represents an essential contribution to the frictionless integration of software and data in energy research.

3.2 Dataset metadata creation

Although some metadata, such as the generation or modification dates, might be automatically generated within publication processes, metadata is mostly created in a manual effort. To support the process of data annotation, initiatives that have developed a specific metadata schema or have introduced one as a standard, often also offer tool support to help with the use of the schema in everyday research.

These are mostly forms that are offered online on web pages or locally as scripts. In them, the individual metadata elements of a schema are queried and converted into well-structured and machine-readable file formats. An example of this is the DataCite Metadata Generator¹⁰. Other tools go beyond this functionality. The Frictionless Framework¹¹, for example, offers functions for the creation of metadata as well as support for their extraction, validation and transformation. A variety of other tools specializing in the generation, analysis, and further processing of metadata along various metadata schemas are publicly collected and listed in the Metadata Standards Directory¹² and Catalog¹³ by the Research Data Alliance (RDA).

Data repositories, such as Zenodo¹⁴, also assist its users in adding metadata to the published content. The platforms also provide forms with many metadata elements organized in categories like basic information, license, funding, contributors, etc. Since not all of the characteristics apply to every usecase, the platforms can differentiate required, recommended, and optional information.

3.3 Dataset metadata publication

When publishing datasets, it is generally sufficient to make the data available on a platform where it can be made available over the long term and easily

⁹<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oemetadata>

¹⁰<https://dhvlab.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/datacite-generator/>

¹¹<https://github.com/frictionlessdata/framework>

¹²<https://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/tools/>

¹³<https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/tool-index>

¹⁴<https://zenodo.org/>

obtained. This location can then be referenced in text publication or from other resources. Furthermore, to make it possible to find the data in a data search, it must be annotated with the richest possible metadata. However, if this metadata is created solely on the platform that also hosts the data, it can only be found by users of that specific platform. To enable broader discoverability, and thus greater potential consumer use, the metadata can be registered in data catalogs. Via data catalogs, content can be found even if the actual data source is unknown to the searcher. Furthermore, searching in a catalog is more efficient than searching through all data platforms individually.

The DBpedia Databus, which was made usable for energy research as part of the project, is such a metadata cataloging platform through which datasets can be registered, described, and found. It enables the description of datasets in a detailed and well-structured way. Metadata entries can be linked to ontologies to use common definitions of the field. Ontologies can be connected to the metadata items to employ their term definitions and dependencies. Furthermore, the embedded versioning system allows for the continuous improvement of datasets by the initial data providers but also by the data consumers. Since the DBpedia Databus does not host the data itself, but only the respective metadata including a link to the data source, the data itself can be hosted on any platform as long as a URL is provided.

The Databus initially only requires a small basic set of meta information, such as author, license or similar, as part of the registration process. Via an additional software layer, the Databus Mods, any additional metadata elements or schemas can be used or even requested, e.g. as domain standards. A web user interface, a REST API, and a straightforward Python script that implements the features of the REST API are all tools that may be used to submit data to the Databus¹⁵. The Metadata Overlay Search System (MOSS)¹⁶, which is based on the mods, can be used to search the extended metadata and find data.

¹⁵<https://github.com/LOD-GEOSS/databus-snippets/wiki/Deploying-to-the-Databus>

¹⁶<https://moss.tools.dbpedia.org/>

4 Description of Individual Database Contents

4.1 Relational databases

In energy systems research, the Open Energy Platform (OEP)¹ provides a central domain-specific data repository in the form of the Open Energy Database (OEDB). The relational database based on PostgreSQL primarily supports tabular data formats and also offers tool support for their annotation with the specially developed OEMetaBuilder², whereby primarily the OE metadata schema is used. The platform offers the possibility to upload data manually via GUI or automatically via a REST API.

Once descriptive metadata has been created for the data and stored in the OEDB, it can also be registered in the DBpedia Databus. This is done via an automated interface developed within this project, submitting a metadata file to the Databus API. The registered metadata record contains a URL that points to the corresponding tables within the relational database. This allows searchers not only to name the OEDB as the source of the data they are looking for, but also to access it individually and directly, e.g. for further processing. The technical effort to implement the mentioned interface between relational database and Databus is low and insignificant compared to the benefit generated by making information from individual data silos findable in a distributed database infrastructure.

4.2 RDF triple stores

Triple stores can also be connected to the database infrastructure via the Databus. In triple stores the data is stored in the format of Resource Description Framework (RDF) triples. RDF is a standard model for representing and organizing data. It provides a structured and flexible way to describe resources and their relationships using a '*Subject - Predicate - Object*' syntax, where the *subject* refers to the resource being described, the *predicate* represents a property of the resource and the *object* represents the value of it which can be a literal or another resource. It enables the creation of semantic models that enhance data interoperability and facilitate meaningful machine understanding of information. Triple stores are specialized databases designed for efficiently storing and querying RDF data. They are scalable and, by leveraging graph-based data structures and indexing techniques to enable fast retrieval

¹<https://openenergy-platform.org/>

²<https://openenergy-platform.org/dataedit/oemetabuilder/>

of information, highly performant in managing large-scale RDF datasets. Due to their ability to handle complex graph relationships, triple stores are able to make use of powerful semantic querying and integration of diverse RDF data sources. SPARQL is a query language designed for querying stored RDF data. It offers a standardized and powerful syntax for retrieving and manipulating RDF data through the expression of complex queries, which enable advanced filtering and joining of data based on structural relationships. Additionally, its support for aggregation, sorting and other highly-sophisticated patterns, it is suitable for data integration and analysis tasks over large-scale RDF datasets.

To connect a general triple store to a distributed database infrastructure, like the Databus, data needs to be transferred between both instances. One approach is to individually implement direct API calls, using the APIs of the triple store and Databus to extract the relevant data from the triple store and transfer it to the Databus. However, this method is error prone due to its complexity. An alternative and more robust approach is to utilize the in this project developed Databus-Client for Python, which provides a structured way to interact with the Databus, simplifying the integration process ([Frey et al. 2021](#)). When setting up or accessing the triple store, the user automatically supplies all metadata needed to be propagated to the Databus. This metadata can be adapted to the Databus syntax by aligning the user's input data with the appropriate Databus-Client constructs.

It should be emphasized that individual data records within a triple store can be annotated with metadata and registered on the Databus via SPARQL queries based on identifying characteristics and independent of other data content. The API URL of the triple store in combination with a corresponding SPARQL query then serves as the target address of the data record, via which it can be found and obtained. In this way, specific information in triple stores can be distinguished, described and made accessible.

5 Integration through Scientific Workflows

5.1 Scientific workflows

Software workflows are composed of multiple calculation steps, which can be manually or ideally automatically chained together, and are crucial for managing and organizing complex tasks and processes efficiently. These steps transform their input data making it available to other processes and can be sequential or have a more complex logic. Well-designed workflows improve reusability and reproducibility of results, as they help to break down complex tasks while describing the necessary subprocesses. By breaking down complex tasks into smaller, manageable subprocesses, workflows improve productivity and maintainability. One of the advantages of software workflows is the potential for automation. By chaining calculation steps, workflows enable the flow of data from one process to another, potentially eliminating the need for manual intervention at each stage. This automation not only saves time but also reduces the potential for human errors, ensuring consistent and reliable results.

Models and Software should be reused and documented as Chapter 2 shows. When interfaces are well documented, they can be reused in different workflows in different combinations. To promote the reusability of individual processing steps, workflows should be designed to be modular, and components that are likely to be deployed in a variety of situations should be documented and provided separately. This also applies to transformation scripts, where a developer needs to have auxiliary steps for data processing and transformation in order to feed data in a correct format to the following step. These scripts should in any way be documented in the same way as other more complex processes. In this context, modularity has a direct positive effect on the reusability of research software.

As a best practice example for this modular concept, the open source tool *Currency Conversion for Python* (CuCoPy)¹ was developed as part of LOD-GEOSS to make it easier to convey currency data into energy systems research software. The tool provides methods for exchanging currencies from more than 260 countries and adjusting monetary values for inflation back until 1960 on a yearly basis. By making this tool available independently under the open MIT license, it is now possible to embed it into the interfaces of databases and models of the energy systems domain by a simple import or to use it flexibly as a stand-alone application in processing workflows. Due to its independence, the currency conversion functions can easily be further developed by the community

¹<https://github.com/FZJ-IEK3-VSA/CuCoPy>

and adapted to their own needs.

5.2 Scientific workflow creation

Workflow management tools have emerged serving valuable functionality to define, streamline, and optimize workflows. These tools make the creation and automation of workflows easier, without needing developers to build robust infrastructures themselves. Some tools offer functionality to work with dependencies, to parallelize steps or even to perform deeper analyses from the processes. Some of the benefits of these tools include:

- Automation
- Dependency management
- Consistency and robustness
- Monitoring and visualization
- Reproducibility
- Scalability
- Flexibility and adaptability

In the following, a subset of the tools are listed with which software workflows can be controlled:

- Snakemake²: Open-source workflow management system for complex data processing and analysis tasks. Uses a Python-based domain-specific language (DSL) and offers automatic parallelization.
- NextFlow³: Open-source workflow management system for scientific and data-intensive applications. Uses a DSL for this and offers automatic parallelization.
- Common Workflow Language (CWL)⁴: Specification and set of standards for describing workflows platform-agnostic. Defines workflows in a text-based language.
- KNIME⁵: Open-source graphical workflow environment that enables the use and integration of workflows for data science. Supports parallel execution.
- Apache Airflow⁶: Open-source platform that allows users to build and schedule workflows, allowing the connection of complex workflows. Supports parallel execution.

²<https://snakemake.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

³<https://www.nextflow.io/>

⁴<https://www.commonwl.org/>

⁵<https://www.knime.com/>

⁶<https://airflow.apache.org/>

- DoIt⁷: Build automation tool in Python. Allows to define tasks and dependencies in a file, that can be used to automate multiple processes.
- Galaxy⁸: Open-source web-based platform that offers an interface for creating and executing workflows visually. Specifically has tools for bioinformatics and genomics.
- Taverna⁹: Open-source workflow management system with GUI to create workflows, specifically for the life sciences domain.
- Maestro¹⁰: Open-source workflow management and orchestration tool, specially used in the computational chemistry and drug discovery fields. Provides a GUI to design and execute workflows, as well as domain-specific tools.

In LOD-GEOSS it was demonstrated, how Snakemake can be utilized to support transparency and reproducibility in complex modeling workflows. The workflow comprises data preparation, optimization, post-processing, and plotting steps and utilizes and combines various building blocks of a distributed data infrastructure.

5.3 Scientific workflow publication

In the previous section, the barrier of reusability was highlighted from a technical perspective. However, a second perspective is discoverability. Even well-designed workflows will not be reused if they cannot be discovered. If workflows are not annotated and shared adequately, e.g. with the help of this project's DataDesc approach, they will not be used by the public. Several platforms exist today that can help developers distribute their work, as well as reuse software that has already been created, therefore not spending efforts on redundant developments. These platforms enable the sharing, dissemination, and publication of workflows in the research community. Centralizing the publication of workflows makes it easier for scientists to discover software and data interesting to their domain. In addition, these public repositories increase the potential for automated discovery tools that could potentially be able to chain different workflows together, if their software and data have been sufficiently documented.

Along characteristics such as their prevalence in a research domain or features such as consistent version management, one can choose among the following platforms, for example:

- WorkflowHub¹¹: It is a registry for describing, sharing, and publishing scientific computational workflows. It makes an extensive use of open

⁷<https://pydoit.org/>

⁸<https://galaxyproject.org/>

⁹<https://incubator.apache.org/projects/taverna.html>

¹⁰<https://maestrowf.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

¹¹<https://workflowhub.eu/>

standards and tools, like CWL, RO-Crate, Bioschemas and GA4GH's TRS API.

- MyExperiment¹²: Used by multiple domains to share and discover scientific workflows and other research items.
- KNIME Hub¹³: platform dedicated to KNIME, which is a graphical workflow environment for data science. Users can share and access workflows, components, and extensions also developed with KNIME.
- Galaxy¹⁴: Platform that allows users from biomedical research to create, share and publish workflows.
- Zenodo, Github, and other platforms: more general software repositories where users store their workflows.

¹²<https://www.myexperiment.org/home>

¹³<https://hub.knime.com/>

¹⁴<https://usegalaxy.org/>

6 Recommendations

This chapter provides recommendations for designing, annotating, and publishing research software and database interfaces, workflows, and datasets. They are based on current best practices and on experience gained during the course of this project. In essence, they are intended to encourage the use of existing research data infrastructure, but also to develop it collaboratively as needed.

6.1 Content design

- **Dataset scopes:** When creating a dataset, its content scope should first be consciously defined and a decision made as to which data it should contain in detail. If this scope is defined very broadly, e.g. by including all heterogeneous data of a model experiment, this may make its subsequent use for other purposes difficult. On the other hand, if a modular approach is taken that groups content independently into separate datasets, their content can be reused more flexibly. Additionally, a more specific scope also allows for more accurate metadata annotation.
- **Dataset formats:** When creating a dataset, care should be taken to use adequate file and database formats. A chosen format should be capable of representing the content structures depicted in the data. For example, it is not advisable to squeeze a multidimensional information structure into a two-dimensional table format. When selecting a format, consideration should also be given to whether metadata should also be mapped inherently in addition to the actual data.
- **Data models:** The structuring of dataset contents should not be done randomly, but along previously defined data models. If possible, data models that are widely used in one's own research area should be used. While individual data transformation and processing methods are also required to process individual data models, existing processing libraries can often be used for standardized data models.
- **Data model development:** If data models are not available for content typical in one's research area, they should be developed and promoted in consensus with the domain community. On their basis, sustainable interface standards can be developed that can be used in a variety of ways due to a common data model.
- **Software interfaces and data models:** The interface of a software should be based on standardized or at least widely used data models in order to minimize the need for transformation and to facilitate the process of

data ingestion. The focus here is on the use of clear and comprehensible data structures. Individual variable types should be specified precisely in order to facilitate integration with other interfaces and data sources.

- **Software interfaces and transformation logic:** It should be avoided to encapsulate transformation logic for the translation of one data model into another within individual software interfaces or database APIs. Even if this allows a software more flexibility in feeding in input data, the developed transformation functions cannot be reused within other applications. It is better practice to provide transformation logic in separate software modules, so that it can be sustainably reused in different use cases.
- **Design of software workflows:** In order to make analyses and model experiments reusable and their results transparent and reproducible, the use of workflow tools is recommended. In order to increase the transparency and traceability of a model experiment, a workflow should include as broad as possible parts of data retrieval and pre- and post-processing in addition to the actual application of research software. All data and software sources should be referenced with specific version numbers. The modular approach, in which even complex data processing chains are broken down into clearly structured and definable work steps, offers the possibility of publishing research methods and results in a transparent and reusable manner and is facilitating the integration of software and data.

6.2 Content annotation

- **Metadata:** Resources of any research data type (including software, data, and workflows) should be described with rich metadata to promote their discoverability, understanding, transparency, and reusability. Descriptive, administrative, structural and provenance information should be equally considered.
- **Metadata schemas:** Annotation of resources should be done along metadata schemas for consistency, comparability, and interoperability. Schemas can be selected based on their particular use within a specific research domain, or based on their cross-domain distribution. Combinations of complementary schemas may be useful to enable a more accurate searching and classification of data.
- **Ontologies:** In an ontology, knowledge is represented in terms of individual, interrelated concepts. The formally defined and classified concepts enable a uniform description and interpretation of models and data. Ontologies should be used to unambiguously classify the information mapped in metadata schemas.
- **Metadata schema and ontology development:** Instead of developing individual schemes and ontologies, it is good practice to utilize existing ones

wherever suitable. If ontologies and metadata standards have not yet become established in one's own domain, the development of such should be supported to further standardize the language and description structures and to enable an unambiguous exchange of information.

6.3 Content publication

- Content selection: To increase the overall transparency and reusability, research content of any data type should be published. This includes software, datasets, workflows, and more. By software, not only larger models are meant, also transformation functions and other processing and automation scripts are worth to be shared.
- Platform selection: To achieve the greatest impact, suitable publication platforms need to be identified for each of the involved research data types. It is not helpful to choose only one platform and publish all content of a project there, as certain types of research data are often only searched on platforms specialized for them. Publishing each component of the material in the proper repository and including connections to similar contents from other repositories is a good practice. In this manner, each individual piece of content can be located in a proper setting while yet allowing for simple access to its larger context.
- Metadata publication: Any metadata should be published with the artifacts they describe. To publish or register the metadata on more than one platform increases the visibility and impact of the published artifacts.

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